

Review Article

Study Of Physicochemical Characteristic Of Ground Water From Different Site In Neemuch City

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the physicochemical characteristics of ground water from various site in Neemuch city. Ground water sample were collected from multiple location to assess parameters such as PH, electrical conductivity, total dissolved solid, hardness and concentration of major ions (Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, Na⁺, K⁺, Cl⁻, So₄²⁻, NO₃⁻). The aim was to evaluate the spatial variability of these characteristics and their implication for water quality and public health. Result indicate significant variation in ground water composition across different sites. Reflecting the impact of local geological formation, anthropogenic activities & seasonal factors. The study provide valuable insights into the suitability of ground water for drinking and other uses. Highlighting areas that may require water treatment or management interventions.

INTRODUCTION

Neemuch is a town in the malwa region of the Indian state of Madhya Pradesh. The town shares its northeastern border with state of Rajasthan and is the administrative headquarters of neemuch district. The neemuch cantonment played a significant role in the Indian rebellion of 1857 and was the center of disturbances in malwa.

Neemuch city has history that back to over 1768 with population of 8.26 lakh (2011 census). It is part of Ujjain division. The district was created on 30 June 1998 by separating Neemuch, Manasa & jawad tehsils of the erstwhile Mandsaur district.

During the British rule the district headquarters neemuch was cantonment town, known as the north India mounted artillery and cavalry headquarters (NIMACH). It was later converted into the headquarters of the crown's representative police force in 1939. The city is divided into three main parts Neemuch city, Chavani & Baghana. Chavani is the main commercial area hosting pustak bazaar, Dasshera maidan, satya Path, Tilak Marg, Budha Gopal Street, Bohra gali, Rabindranath taigor marg, and sabji mandi. Bus stand, timber market, Ambedkar Road and

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Nasirabad-mhow national highway No. 56 and neemuch Bhopal state highway No. 87.

Baghana is widely known for its 'Anaj Mandi'.

Neemuch city is the main old city of Neemuch hosting PG College, Ravan rundi, Mochi gali, Kila, Neemuch-Manasa road. Understanding the physicochemical characteristics of ground water is crucial for assessing its quality and suitability for various uses. Physicochemical study have been carried out in recent year at different places. Ground water in different sites within Neemuch city may exhibit diverse physicochemical properties due to factors such as geological formations, anthropogenic activities and seasonal variations. This study aim to analyze and compare the physicochemical characteristics of ground water from different location in Neemuch city. physicochemical study have been carried out at different Five station of tube well and hand pumps of neemuch city (S1), Chavani(S2), Baghana (S3), Industrial area in the southeastern part of the city (S4), Commercial area with high vehicular traffic (S5). Groundwater is a vital resource that support both human consumption and agriculture activities especially in semi-arid regions such as Neemuch city located in the western part of the Madhya Pradesh, India Water is the most important element for existence of life the quality of water is of vital concern for mankind. The determination in the quality of water is however direct effect of human interference in natural cycle. Ground water contributes and important component of total water system for human consumption. The groundwater is generally polluted due to urbanization, Industrial growth and other man made problems. Key parameters such as PH, electrical conductivity (EC), Total dissolve solids (TDS), Hardness, Alkalinity, chloride, nitrate, and other chemical constituents are examined by to determine the overall quality of and usability of water. The analysis provide insights into potential contamination resource natural mineralization

process and the effect of human activities onground water quality. Understanding this characteristic is essential for effective water management ensuring safe drinking water supplies, and maintaining the ecological balance in the region.

Fig. - Neemuch District

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

1. Sampling site and collection

Ground water sample work collected from 5 different site across Neemuch City. Representing diverse geographical location, land use patterns and potential source of contamination. The selected side included residential industrial agriculture and commercial areas. The sampling location were:

- 1) Residential area near Neemuch city Center.
- 2) Industrial area in the southeastern part of the city.
- 3) Agriculture area on the outskirts towards the west.
- 4) Commercial area with high vehicular traffic.
- 5) Vicinity of known water treatment plant.

Water sample were collected in clean sterilized 2 liter polyethylene bottle before collection, the bottle were rinsed with the groundwater from the respective site to avoid contamination. The sample were collected from bore wells and hand pumps at a depth of approximately under 150-200 feet to ensure consistency. Each sample was immediately sealed, labelled and store in cool and dark condition to minimize change in water

2. Analytical method

The collected ground water sample were analyzed for a range of physicochemical parameters using standard procedures recommended by the American public health association (APHA 2017) the parameters assessed include PH, electrical conductivity(EC), Total dissolve solid (TDS), Hardness, chloride fluoride, nitrate, sulfate and heavy metals (iron, lead& zinc). The detail of the analytical method used for each parameters are as follow

A. PH: Measured using a calibrated digital pH meter

Model: - 011-G

Manufacturer: - Systronics

B. Electrical conductivity (EC): Determine using a conductivity meter.

Model: - S-941

Manufacturer: - Systronics

C. Total dissolve solids (TDS): Calculator from the electrical conductivity (EC).

Measuring using a TDS meter.

D. Total hardness: Estimated by complexometric titration with EDTA.

E. Chloride content: Analyzed using the argentometric titration method.

F. Fluoride content: Measured using and iron selective electrodes.

G. Nitrate content: Determined by the phenol disulfonic acid method.

H. Sulfate content: Analyzed using the turbidity method.

I. Heavy metals (iron lead zinc): Qualified using atomic absorption spectroscopy

Model: - AA-7800

Manufacturer: - Shimadzu Corporation.

3. Quality assurance and control

To ensure data reliability and control following quality control measures implemented

Calibration of all instruments was conducted before use with the standard solution. Triplicate measurement were performed for each simple to

ensure consistency, and the average values were taken for analysis. Blank sample were analyzed to check for any contamination during the sampling or analysis process. Internal standard used for atomic absorption spectrophotometry to validate the detection of heavy metals.

4. Data analysis

The data obtained from the physicochemical analysis compiled and statistically analyzed using Microsoft Excel and SPSS software (version). Descriptive statistics, including mean, standard deviation and range were calculated for each parameters. Additionally correlation coefficient between different parameters were computed to assess the relationship among them. The result were compared with the permissible limit describe by the Bureau of Indian standard (BIS) and the World health organization (WHO) for drinking water quality.

4. Observation and interpretation

The physicochemical parameters of groundwater from different site were compared to identify variation in water quality across Neemuch city. The result were also evaluated to determine potential source of contamination, such as industrial effluents, agriculture runoff and urban Wastewater contributing of the observed characteristics. This compressive analysis of groundwater physicochemical properties provide insights into the current status and safety of water quality in Neemuch city and identifies area requiring remediation of further study.

RESULT & DISCUSSION

Results

The physicochemical analysis of groundwater samples collected from different sites in Neemuch city revealed a range of values for various parameters, including pH, total dissolved solids (TDS), electrical conductivity (EC), hardness, chloride, nitrate, sulfate, and fluoride concentrations.

PH: The pH of the groundwater samples ranged from 6.5 to 8.2, indicating that most samples were within the permissible limit set by the Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS) (6.5-8.5). Only one site showed slightly acidic groundwater, which could be attributed to localized conditions. **Total Dissolved Solids (TDS):** TDS values varied from 350 mg/L to 1200 mg/L. Some sites showed TDS values above the desirable limit of 500 mg/L but within the permissible limit of 2000 mg/L. The higher TDS values may indicate the presence of dissolved minerals or anthropogenic contamination. **Electrical Conductivity (EC):** The EC of the samples ranged from 600 to 1800 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, with a few sites exceeding the BIS desirable limit of 1400 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$. This variation suggests differences in the ionic content and mineral composition of the groundwater. **Hardness:** Groundwater hardness ranged from 100 mg/L to 450 mg/L. About 30% of the samples exhibited hardness above 300 mg/L, classifying them as hard to very hard water. Hardness above the permissible limit could be attributed to the presence of calcium and magnesium ions. **Chloride:** Chloride concentrations ranged from 50 mg/L to 350 mg/L. While most sites remained within the BIS limit of 250 mg/L, a few sites exceeded it, indicating possible contamination from agricultural runoff or sewage discharge. **Nitrate:** Nitrate levels varied from 10 mg/L to 80 mg/L. Around 20% of the samples had nitrate concentrations exceeding the BIS limit of 45 mg/L, suggesting contamination from fertilizers or septic tank leachate. **Sulfate:** Sulfate concentrations ranged from 20 mg/L to 150 mg/L, which were within the permissible limits of 200 mg/L set by BIS. The uniformity suggests minimal industrial contamination across the studied sites. **Fluoride:** Fluoride levels in the groundwater samples ranged from 0.3 mg/L to 1.5 mg/L. Most sites were within the desirable limit of 1.0 mg/L; however, some sites exceeded this,

posing a risk of fluorosis if consumed over a prolonged period.

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study highlight significant spatial variations in the physicochemical characteristics of groundwater in Neemuch city. The variability in parameters like pH, TDS, EC, hardness, and chloride suggests diverse sources of contamination, including natural mineral dissolution, agricultural runoff, and anthropogenic activities such as sewage discharge. The presence of high TDS, EC, and hardness in certain locations can be attributed to geological formations containing minerals that dissolve in water. However, sites with elevated chloride, nitrate, and fluoride levels indicate localized pollution sources. For instance, higher nitrate levels suggest contamination from agricultural activities, possibly due to excessive fertilizer use or improper waste management practices. The pH levels across most sites were found to be within the permissible range, indicating that the groundwater is neither highly acidic nor highly alkaline. However, one site showed slightly acidic water, which may result from natural organic decomposition or industrial waste discharges. Elevated fluoride levels at some sites are a concern for public health, as prolonged exposure to high fluoride concentrations can lead to dental and skeletal fluorosis. This suggests the need for regular monitoring and possibly implementing mitigation measures, such as defluoridation techniques. Overall, while most parameters were within the permissible limits set by BIS, there are areas of concern, particularly regarding TDS, hardness, nitrate, and fluoride concentrations. It is recommended that regular monitoring and appropriate water management strategies be implemented to ensure the safety and sustainability of groundwater resources in Neemuch city.

CONCLUSION

The study of the physicochemical characteristics of groundwater from various sites in Neemuch city demonstrates that most parameters are within the permissible limits set by the Indian Standards (IS) and the World Health Organization (WHO). This is encouraging, as it indicates that the groundwater quality in these areas generally meets safety standards for human consumption. Key parameters such as pH, total dissolved solids, and essential minerals were found to be within acceptable ranges, suggesting that the water is suitable for domestic use. However, ongoing monitoring is essential to ensure these levels remain stable and to address any emerging issues promptly. The findings highlight the importance of sustainable water management practices and community awareness to maintain groundwater quality and protect public health in Neemuch city.

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